

Towards maximal unification of semantically diverse ontologies for controversial domains

Abstract

Purpose – Ontologies are prone to wide semantic variability due to subjective points of view of their composers. This study aims to propose a new approach for maximal unification of diverse ontologies for controversial domains by their relations.

Design/methodology/approach – Effective matching or unification of multiple ontologies for a specific domain is crucial for the success of many semantic web applications, such as semantic information retrieval and organization, document tagging, summarization and search. To this end, numerous automatic and semi-automatic techniques were proposed in the past decade that attempt to identify similar entities, mostly classes, in diverse ontologies for similar domains. Apparently, matching individual entities cannot result in full integration of ontologies' semantics without matching their inter-relations with all other related classes (and instances). However, semantic matching of ontological relations still constitutes a major research challenge. Therefore, in this paper we propose a new paradigm for assessment of maximal possible matching and unification of ontological relations. To this end, several unification rules for ontological relations were devised based on ontological reference rules, and lexical and textual entailment. These rules were semi-automatically implemented to extend a given ontology with semantically matching relations from the other ontology for a similar domain. Then, the ontologies were unified through these similar pairs of relations. We observe that these rules can be also facilitated to reveal the contradictory relations in different ontologies.

Findings - To assess the feasibility of our approach two experiments were conducted with different sets of multiple personal ontologies on controversial domains constructed by trained subjects. Our results for about fifty distinct ontology pairs demonstrate a good potential of our methodology for increasing inter-ontology agreement. Furthermore, we show that the presented methodology can lead to a complete unification of multiple semantically heterogeneous ontologies.

Research limitations - This is a conceptual study that presents a new approach for semantic unification of ontologies by a devised set of rules along with the initial experimental evidence of its feasibility and effectiveness. However this methodology has to be fully automatically implemented and tested on a larger dataset in future research.

Practical implications - This result has implication for semantic search, since a richer ontology comprised of multiple aspects and viewpoints of the domain of knowledge enhances discoverability and improves search results.

Originality/value - To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to examine and assess the maximal level of semantic relation-based ontology unification.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, ontologies are widely used as a formal domain vocabulary for content-specific agreements in a variety of knowledge-sharing activities, such as, information organization, retrieval and tagging (Gruber, 1993). However, in the current state of the Semantic Web for many domains there are multiple diverse ontologies rather than one standard vocabulary. Apparently, when using several ontologies in a common application, mismatches can create incoherent results for the users (d'Aquin, 2009). Reaching agreement between these ontologies has become a big challenge, since typically ontologies are created by humans and

Corresponding author:

Maayan Zhitomirsky-Geffet, Department of Information Science, Ramat Gan, Israel, 5290002
Maayan.Zhitomirsky-Geffet@biu.ac.il

thus depend on their view of the world. This situation, where distinct terms and relations are used to express the same ontological knowledge is referred in the literature as *semantic heterogeneity* (Euzenat and Shvaiko, 2007).

To overcome this problem a variety of ontology matching, mapping, merging and alignment algorithms were presented in the past decade (Shvaiko and Euzenat, 2013; Flouris et al., 2008). These systems usually focus on mapping individual concepts (and/or their taxonomic structures) of one ontology to similar concepts in the other one. However, such methods do not lead to a complete unification of ontologies unless all the direct and indirect inter-relations binding these concepts can be consistently unified as well. Furthermore, the domain semantic knowledge is mostly expressed by relations or statements, which are RDF-style triples linking two concepts by some semantic relationships: (*concept1*, *relationship*, *concept2*), e.g. (*Prime minister*, *supports*, *social justice*), rather than by individual entities (concepts and properties). Therefore, if two ontologies comprise similar or non-contradictory sets of statements on the domain they can be fully unified. Also, it can be observed (see Figure 1) that sometimes the individual entities are not semantically identical or similar but the relations including them are similar or entailing in meaning, and thus are matching. Note that entity matching patterns do not apply to relations. For example, given that a concept *C* ("Prime Minister") is one of the domain concepts of a property *P* ("supports") and concepts *D* ("Social protest") and *E* ("Renewable energy research") are in the range of *P*, it still does not mean that there is a relation $T=("Prime Minister", "supports", "Social protest")$ binding *C*, *P* and *D* (or some of these concepts' sub-concepts or instances) together, since *C* and *D* are not the only concepts in the domain and range of *P*. Furthermore, these relations represent the entity contexts, or set of facts expressed by ontologies and thus reflect their semantic level which cannot be directly derived from comparing their entities and taxonomical structures. On the other hand, sometimes there is no direct matching at the entity level but the relations of the two ontologies can be semantically matched as illustrated by Figure 1. On the other hand, matching isolated entities might lead to incoherent relations in the unified ontology as shown in (Meilicke and Stuckenschmidt, 2008). In addition, typical semantically rich ontologies include many more non-hierarchical domain specific relations than taxonomical ones (IS-A). Currently, matching and unification of non-taxonomic relations is an underexplored topic which constitutes a major research challenge and requires a deeper level of analysis and understanding. Reaching consensus on ontologies becomes even harder when the domain is highly controversial, involving diverse opinions, for example (as typical in news articles) political, cultural or religious aspects. These domains can be considered as the "worst case" in regards with enhancement of inter-ontology matching and unification.

Figure 1. Given the fragments of two ontologies, the existing ontology matching approaches will only be able to achieve a partial match between them by mapping two concepts labeled as "Prime Minister" as shown on the left-side diagram. On the other hand, the proposed entailment based method will allow for fully matching these ontology fragments by mapping between all the entailing relations (triples), as can be seen on the right-side diagram. Note that the meaning of the relation "Prime Minister, Leader-of, Government" semantically entails the meaning of "Prime Minister, IS-A, Head of Government" and the meaning of the relation "Prime Minister, IS-A, Politician" is semantically entailed by "Prime Minister, IS-A, Head-of-Government", since the meaning of the concept "Head-of-Government" lexically entails the meaning of "Politician".

Thus, the goal of this study is to develop a generic approach for semantic ontology unification based on matching and integration of sets of statements conveyed by ontological relations. Consequently, this paper addresses the following main research question: Whether and how is it possible to maximize inter-ontology agreement by matching and unification of their relations?

Following the above rationale, we introduce a new paradigm for relation-level ontology matching and unification for controversial domains. The main idea behind the proposed methodology is to identify the maximal common set of relations (statements on the domain) that can be expressed by two ontologies, and then to check whether the rest of the relations complement (and do not contradict) each other. The meaning of such unification is that in the case of a lack of contradictions the two ontologies can be fully unified into one semantically consistent model, since despite their differences at the entity level they express the same and/or complementary set of facts on the domain. On the other hand, if some contradictory relations were detected they can be inter-linked and marked up as different viewpoints on the similar subject. Such a multi-viewpoint ontology can be further utilized for multi-viewpoint information tagging (Ouzrout et al., 2009), multi-viewpoint information retrieval (Powell and French, 1998; Geryville, 2007), and multi-viewpoint information document summarization (Paul et al, 2010).

Further, this research aims to employ the proposed relation-based unification paradigm to answer the following questions:

- What kind of impact on human agreement on ontologies is made by various types of pre-supplied information and knowledge sources?
- Whether and how various viewpoints are reflected in ontologies?

Finally, to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed paradigm we conducted two initial experiments on different sets of personal ontologies for highly controversial domains: a social protest in Israel and the Jewish tradition. A semi-automatic analysis of the relations in both ontology sets according to the presented paradigm revealed a high potential for a complete unification. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In the next section we present a review of related literature. Our approach: a new paradigm to ontology unification is introduced in sections 3. Section 4 presents our experimental setting; the empirical results are shown and discussed in Section 5 and the conclusions are stated in Section 6.

2. Related work

Standardization of domain vocabulary is a crucial task for semantic web services and applications. Two main approaches exist to achieve this goal: (1) alignment or matching of entities (concepts and properties) of two different ontologies for the same domain; (2) merging or unification of several existing ontologies into one model.

Ontology matching is defined as finding correspondences or semantic relationships between their entities (Euzenat et al., 2011). Euzenat and Valtchev (2003) classify the various existing measures into the following types: terminological, (T), string-based matching and terminological with lexicons, i.e. considering synonym as equivalent and hyponyms as subsumed; internal structure comparison, (I), comparing the value range or cardinality of their attributes); external structure comparison, (S) - comparing the location of the concept in the taxonomy; extensional comparison, (E), comparing the set of other entities that are attached to them (in general instances of classes); semantic comparison (M) comparing the interpretations of the entities. In the past decade, numerous studies were conducted that employ the internal taxonomical structure of the ontologies to identify matching concepts and then develop ontology similarity measures considering the amount of these matching concepts (Maedche and Staab (2002); Cheng et al., 2011; David and Euzenat, 2008; Farooq et al., 2010; Madhavan, et al., 2001; Chaffee and Gauch, 2000; Ngan et al., 2009; Liu and Gruen, 2008; Staab, 2011; Xu, et al., 2012; Akbari and Fathian, 2010; Alasoud et al., 2009; Pirro and Talia, 2008; Euzenat and Shvaiko, 2007; Euzenat et al., 2011; Shvaiko and Euzenat, 2013).).

Finally, a recent article by Scharffe et al. (2013) introduces *ontology alignment patterns* that summarize the terminological and structural matching approach for ontological entities such as concepts, properties (relationships) and instances. In these patterns the relationship similarity is based on the number of similar concepts in their ranges and domains.

However, as exemplified in Figure 1 above many semantically similar statements contained in two ontologies might be missed by the entity-based approach. Therefore, matching individual entities is insufficient for reaching maximal or full unification of ontologies. Hence, the above reviewed techniques are to be extended for identifying semantically similar relations can leverage the matching level of ontologies which is the focus of the current research. Nevertheless, relation matching, i.e. matching of RDF-style triples: (concept A, property/relationship, concept B) (including non-taxonomic relationship types), that captures the statement-level semantic similarities seems to be underexplored in the literature. For example, the two relations: (Prime Minister, Leader-of, Government) and (Prime Minister, IS-A, Head of Government) convey similar semantic information (statements) while two out of three of their entities are semantically different.

A first step towards this goal was implemented by d'Aquin (2009) who proposed agreement and disagreement measures which calculate the exact or partial terminological matches (same terms but different relationship type) between RDF-style triples of the form: (term A, property/relationship, term B), i.e.

relation-based matching. However, this agreement measure does not use sophisticated techniques to recognize semantically (but not terminologically) similar entities, as those presented in the above works on entity matching. Therefore, in this research we suggest to enhance relation-based matching (as in (d'Aquin, 2009)) with the concept and property matching patterns as in (Scharffe et al., 2013), external information based semantic similarity techniques (as in (Mazuel and Sabouret, 2008)), and additional inference rules as described in section 3.

Our further goal is to merge the ontologies into the unified model based on the found matching relations. Therefore we next review the main unification approaches that exist in the literature.

For this purpose, two basic methodologies were applied (de Bruijn et al., 2006): (1) The integrated ontology is a *union* of the given ontologies; (2) The merged ontology is an *intersection* of the given ontologies. In the first (union) approach all entities in both source ontologies are included in the unified model, where differences in representation of similar concepts have been resolved. This approach was applied in (Xie et al., 2011). The authors map objects of an ontology to a tree structure, restructure the tree, and rely on the tree structure to integrate ontologies through attribute comparison. Another method for merging the taxonomical trees with concepts as nodes was proposed by (Op't Land et al., 2009). This work presented the Glue system which finds mappings between these concepts, assuming that every node in the taxonomy tree has a match, and computes the joint probability distribution for every node. The intersection-based unified ontology consists only of the parts of the source ontologies which overlap. This methodology was adopted in (Dieng and Hug, 1998) to automatically generate a common ontology of several experts from their personal ontologies. They employ algorithms for matching synonyms, similar terms and topological structures. Likewise, the PROMPT system (Noy and Musen, 2003) is one of the most prominent tools for merging ontologies based on their similar concepts (classes). PROMPT identifies a number of ontology merging operations (e.g. merge classes/concepts, merge properties, merge bindings between a property and a class), a number of possible conflicts and finds possible solutions to these conflicts and displays them to the user. The intersection approach was also employed in several works on collaborative ontology integration, such as (Heflin, 2001; Holsapple and Joshi, 2002; Karaparis, 2012). In these studies the participants went through an iterative process of disagreement revision and discussion until all the controversial viewpoints were eliminated.

In our case, as we aim to reach the maximal agreement on the examined ontologies, the union approach for ontology unification was adopted. As we describe in the next section, the differences in representations of similar relations are resolved by adding the matching relation into both ontologies, and by marking the contradicting relations as viewpoints.

3. A new paradigm for maximal ontology unification by statements

The primary goal of this study is to explore whether amplifying the matching level between statements (relations) of diverse ontologies could further lead to their full or exhaustive integration. Our preliminary data analysis reveals three types of correspondences between statements of two ontologies:

- (1) Matching statements common for both ontologies;
- (2) Unmatched complementary statements;
- (3) Contradictory inconsistent statements.

3.1. Relation unification rules

First, to increase the inter-ontology matching and similarity level we devised a multi-level unification scheme which comprises a set of six generic *unification rules*. The presented rules should be applied to identify the

maximal subset of matching statements from two or more ontologies and unify them. These rules also utilize the RDF entailment rules from the RDF Semantics specification (Hayes and McBride, 2004) and extend the ontology alignment design patterns (Scharffe et al., 2013) for the case of statement alignment. The RDF(S) entailment rules are typically exploited by delta calculation techniques which compute the differences between the triple sets of different versions of the ontology (Zeginis et al., 2011; Berners-Lee and Connolly, 2004). As opposed to these works, in our case, the RDF(S) entailment rules help reveal additional matching triples (statements) and increase the overall inter-ontology similarity. The unification procedure is performed by extending the ontologies with matching relations from other ontologies.

The following rules should be executed sequentially as each step is an extension of the ontology unification level based on the previous unification steps.

Rule 1: Lexical and morphological unification rule (corresponds to T category in (Euzenat and Valtchev (2003))):

- (1) *Vocabulary normalization* – Typos, different accepted spellings (e.g. color and colour in English), morphological variations, e.g. single vs. plural form, are replaced by a standard form.
- (2) *Synonym substitution* – In both, classes and relationship types, similar terms should be detected and unified, i.e. replaced by a single representative term, e.g. "takes part" – "participates", "protest action" – "protest event".

To automate this rule, external information to the ontology is to be utilized to resolve the terminological differences between ontologies. To this end, numerous WordNet-based measures of similarity can be adopted. For instance, Mazuel and Sabouret (2008) report improved results for their property-based similarity measure using WordNet (Fellbaum, 2008) part-of relationships. Agirre and Rigau (1996) devised a conceptual density formula based on WordNet inter-term relationships and successfully applied it for the task of the word sense disambiguation. (van Assem et al., 2006) used the WordNet synsets and relationships to construct a rich RDF/OWL ontology that can further serve the Semantic web research community. Zesch and Gurevych (2010) experimented with a variety of term similarity metrics based on WordNet and on "wisdom of crowds" resources like Wikipedia. They found comparable results for both resources when employing only the first paragraph of Wikipedia pages. In (Ehrig et al., 2005) the authors incorporate concept usage in context in textual corpora, since semantically similar concepts are used in similar contexts and good measures need to consider semantics and not just structure of the ontologies. Alternatively, microtask crowdsourcing can be employed for collaborative term matching as in (Sarasua et al., 2012).

Statement unification rules based on RDF(S) entailment and inheritance rules:

Rule 2: Transitivity unification – For every class in the ontology, O, for all its subclasses and instances look (recursively) if they are related directly or indirectly by the `rdfs:subClassOf` relationship in the second ontology, O', and vice versa, for every class in O', search O for triples which relate its subclasses or instances by `rdfs:subClassOf` relationship (directly or indirectly). For example, the first ontology contains the triples: (Passover, `rdfs:sinstanceOf`, Jewish Holiday) and (Jewish holiday, `rdfs:subClassOf`, Holiday) while the second one only includes: (Passover, `rdfs:sinstanceOf`, Holiday). Thus, these 3 triples can be added to both ontologies and pairwise unified. This inference pattern corresponds to RDFS rules 9 and 11 (Hayes and McBride, 2004): If (V `rdf:type` U) and (U `rdfs:subClassOf` X) then (V `rdf:type` X); If (U `rdfs:subClassOf` V) and (V `rdfs:subClassOf` X) then (U `rdfs:subClassOf` X). The same rules can be applied on some

other relationship types, e.g. part-of, cause, and location which conform to transitivity characteristics as well.

- Rule 3: Inverse relationship unification – To resolve the problem stated in (Maedche and Staab, 2002) if a statement is expressed by two inversed triples in different ontologies, they should be considered as identical and both of them should be added to both ontologies and then unified, e.g. (Parliament, has-a, deputy), (deputy, member_of, Parliament). If $((U \ X \ V)$ and $(Y \ owl:inverseOf \ X))$ then $(V \ Y \ U)$ (OWL inverse property is defined in <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl-ref/>).
- Rule 4: Property inheritance unification – As determined in Noy and McGuinness (2001) all the instances and subclasses of the class inherit all its properties (in our case relationship types or predicates in RDF triples). This principle was also applied in RO measure of Maedche and Staab (2002) which incorporates inheritance of relationships range and domain values through the taxonomy. For example, (deputy, member_of, Parliament) – (Prime Minister, member_of, Parliament). More formally, if $((X \ rdfs:domain \ V)$ and $((U \ rdfs:subClassOf \ V)$ or $(U \ rdf:type \ V)))$ then $(X \ rdfs:domain \ U)$; if $((X \ rdfs:range \ V)$ and $(U \ rdfs:subClassOf \ V)$ or $(U \ rdf:type \ V)))$ then $(X \ rdfs:range \ U)$. All the derived statements should be added to both ontologies and unified.
- Rule 5: Entailment unification –
- (a) Lexical level entailment (inspired by the lexical entailment definition by (Geffet and Dagan, 2005)) - After applying the above rules, for each triple T from ontology, O, search for occurrences of entailing triples in ontology O', with identical or entailing classes (e.g. their subclasses or instances), and entailing relationships, such that T's relationship is a sub-property of the relationships of the triples in O'. Repeat the same processing for O' as a source ontology and O as a target one. Once detected the corresponding triples should be added to both ontologies and can be unified. For example, member-of and head-of relationships can be considered as sub-properties of part-of, e.g. (Prime Minister, head_of, government) and (Prime Minister, part_of, government). This entailment-based unification is supported by the RDFS rules 9, 11 (formulated earlier), and also by rules 5 and 7 (Hayes and McBride, 2004): if $((U \ rdfs:subPropertyOf \ V)$ and $(V \ rdfs:subPropertyOf \ X)$ then $(U \ rdfs:subPropertyOf \ X)$; if $((X \ rdfs:subPropertyOf \ Y)$ and $(U \ X \ V))$ then $(U \ Y \ V)$. In this context, properties which entail other properties might also be considered as their sub-properties, such as the meaning of "participates_in" (organization, participates_in, social_protest) entails the meaning of "supports" (organization, supports, social_protest) and so it is its sub-property.
 - (b) Unification by textual entailment (as defined in Dagan et al., 2009) - This extended entailment unification rule applies when the truth of one triple (a hypothesis) can be inferred from the truth of the second one (a text) as a whole, despite the fact that all the individual entities participating in these triples might be different. For instance, the text $T=(social \ movement \ leadership, \ demands, \ home \ price \ reduction)$ textually entails the hypothesis $H=(social \ movement \ demonstration, \ protests_against, \ price \ increase)$. To implement this rule automatically systems like BIUTEE (Stern and Dagan, 2012) and Excitement open source platform for automatic recognition of textual entailment (<http://hlfbk.github.io/Excitement-Open-Platform/>) might be adopted and extended. In particular, BIUTEE follows the transformation based paradigm, which recognizes textual entailment by converting the text into the hypothesis via a sequence of transformations. Such a sequence is performed over the syntactic representation of the text - the text's parse tree(s). A transformation modifies a given parse tree, resulting in a generation of a

new parse tree, which can be further modified by subsequent transformations. According to this approach, for the above example, the following transformations will be required: (1) (demand X reduction) entails (protest_against X increase); (2) "demonstration" entails "leadership".

Rule 6: Unification of compatible statements – As a last step towards similar statements detection and unification, we unify triples with similar or entailing classes (or instances) but non-entailing relationships if they do not contradict each other. For instance, (social justice, goal_of, social protest) – (social justice, reason_for, social protest) – (social justice, made_by, social protest). These statements should be added to all the ontologies and then unified respectively.

It should be emphasized that the main innovations and contributions of the devised unification rules are that (a) they are designed for ontological statement (rather than entities) unification; and (b) employ the lexical and textual entailment paradigm for the task of semantic ontology matching, which to the best of our knowledge has not yet been performed in previous research.

3.2. Inconsistency detection rules

Next, inspired by the above unification rules we also devise a new inconsistency test for ontologies in order to effectively capture the third type of correspondences between statements – the contradictory ones. The existing research (e.g. Fahad et al., 2012) analyses the types of inconsistencies at the entity level but does not resolve relation-level conflicts. We hypothesize that possible types of semantic relation-based contradictions in the multi-viewpoint environment emerge from partially matching relations (such as containing both similar or entailing concepts and non-entailing relationships) and thus can be detected by violation of the introduced entailment matching and unification rules.

We argue that three possible types of inconsistencies emerge from partially matching statements and can be revealed by violation of the unification rules 2-6:

- (1) Violation of the "transitivity unification" rule (Rule 2): one of the triple's classes, *C*, (or instances) is a direct or indirect subclass of (or type of) the other class, *D*, in ontology *O*, while in ontology *O'*, *D* is a direct or indirect subclass of *C*. This type of inconsistency can also appear for other transitive relationships such as "part-of". For instance, (music, part-of, art) vs. (art, part-of, music).
- (2) Violation of the "entailment unification" rule (Rule 5): one of the triple classes (or instances) and the relationship type are identical or entailing in both ontologies and the other class in the source ontology, *O*, is antonym or disjoint with the corresponding one in the target ontology, *O'* (Flouris et al., 2008). At the textual level, if some statement in ontology, *O*, is true, then some other statement in ontology *O'* is false. For example, (social protest, cause, economic growth) vs. (social protest, cause, economic crisis).
- (3) Violation of the "unification of compatible statements" rule (Rule 6): for triples with similar or entailing classes (or instances) but contradictory or incompatible relationships. As in the case of (President, attacks, social protest) vs. (President, supports, social protest). This also covers the cases of violation of Rules 3 and 4 ("inverse relationship unification" and "property inheritance unification").

Pairs of triples detected by one of the above rules should be marked as "controversial" and then can be added to the unified ontology. The rest of the triples which were not unified during the unification process are completely distinct in their meaning, since they did not match any unification rule, i.e. neither

they nor their classes semantically relate to or entail each other and thus they cannot contradict. Therefore, they ought to be consistent and complementary and as such can be all included in the unified ontology.

Experimental methodology

To empirically assess the applicability and efficacy of the introduced paradigm for ontology unification by statements, we conducted two independent experiments. The main goal of the arranged experiments is to show the maximal potential improvement in agreement between the diverse ontologies, for which the baseline matching level is very low.

In our experiments the participants were graduate students who took the Semantic Web class at our institution in the years 2010, 2011 and were specifically trained in the task of ontology construction. The ontologies were constructed in Hebrew, since Hebrew was the first language of most of the participants. The participants were instructed to submit the created ontology as a set of RDF-style triples: (class1, relationship type, class2) representing different facts on the domain like in d'Aquin (2009).

The first group included ten participants who were divided into five pairs. Each pair was asked to build an ontology for a particular news topic "Israeli citizen's social protest during the summer of 2011" based on online articles from a given news site. Hence, the vocabulary was not only determined by the given topic but also limited by the particular news sites, associated with varying political viewpoints (inn.co.il, ynet.co.il, nrg.co.il, haaretz.co.il, kikarhashabat.co.il). Each pair was given a different news site. The cooperation of the pair was supposed to help find a consensus in problematic cases and build a more complete and objective ontology.

The second group of nine subjects was given a list of 100 terms (classes) randomly chosen from about 350 classes of the ontology constructed by 3 experts for the domain of the "Jewish tradition" based on user tags in our previous study (Zhitomirsky-Geffet et al., 2010) and a list of 16 relationship types. We randomly chose a few terms for each subtopic of the domain. So they only had to decide which pairs of classes are to be connected and with which type of relationship in order to create ontological triples (or statements). The predefined relationships types help solve the problem of varying relationship names. Each of these subjects had to work alone to assure they do not influence each other's decisions. In this experiment the participants were instructed to create ontologies that reflect their subjective point of view on the given topic, which depends on political and religious views of the subject.

We intentionally did not provide the subjects with predefined class taxonomies since as shown by Maedche and Staab (2002) subjects participating in experiments find it extremely difficult to extend existing taxonomies. In both groups the subjects did not have to construct a full taxonomy of the domain but only what they saw as useful and create up to 100 triples. Note that unlike the previous work above in our setting there were two disjoint groups of subjects who worked offline, did not see and were not affected by each other's or their own ontologies from the other experiment and worked on different domains.

It can be observed that the subjects in two groups were given different starting points to base their ontologies on (news sites vs. fixed vocabulary) in order to learn what types of pre-supplied knowledge might lead to a higher inter-ontology matching and similarity. To increase the number of matching statements and then check for existence of contradictory statements the unification rules presented in Section 3 were employed. Rules 1 and 5 was executed manually by two independent human experts in order to ensure the broadest and most accurate basis for potential matching at the lexical level and also since there are no available automatic lexical databases or textual entailment acquisition tools that could be applied especially for the chosen narrow domains in Hebrew. The rest of the rules' inferences were implemented by a semi-automatic procedure. The automatically derived triples (based on partial lexical matches after manual

normalization by Rule 1) were independently examined and approved for unification or contradiction by two human experts.

Further, the obtained results after applying the above unification rules were compared to the baseline of the d'Aquin (2009) state-of-the-art approach for relation-based ontology matching. To this end, d'Aquin's (2009) ontology agreement measure was used to compute the baseline matching rates. Given two ontologies, O_1 and O_2 which contain sets of statements (triples of the form (term1, relationship, term2)), ST_1 and ST_2 , respectively:

$$agreement(O_1, O_2) = \frac{\sum_{st \in ST_1} agreement(st, O_2) + \sum_{st \in ST_2} agreement(st, O_1)}{|ST_1| + |ST_2|},$$

Where $\sum_{st \in ST_i} agreement(st, O_j)$ sums up the number of exactly identical triples in O_i and O_j with the number of partially identical triples in O_i and O_j (i.e. the triples with identical terms but different relationships).

5. Results and discussion

For the first group of 10 students who had to build an ontology based on various news sites on the subject of "social protest in Israel in the summer of 2011": 5 ontologies were constructed, ontology 1 consists of 118 triples (based on ynet.co.il), ontology 2 – (based on nrg.co.il) 208 triples, 3 – (based on kikarhashabbat.co.il) 91 triples, 4 (based on inn.co.il) – 50 triples, 5 (based on haaretz.co.il) – 97 triples. All 5 ontologies together contain 83 distinct relationship types (the most popular are instance_of (159), is_a (94) and part_of (59). Thirty three (47%) of the relationship types appear only in one ontology. Altogether the ontologies contain 327 distinct terms, 16 of them are common for more than two ontologies, 2 are common for all five ontologies (Tel-Aviv, demonstration). The most popular terms were: Tel-Aviv, demonstration, Benjamin Netanyahu, Itzik Shmuli (a leader of the social protest), Prime minister, protest, tents protest, real estate protest, Rothshild avenue (main site of the social protest), Dafni Lif (a leader of the social protest), deputy, country, Jerusalem, artist, city, student, leaders of the social protest. These terms constitute the core ontology vocabulary.

There are 569 distinct triples in all the ontologies and 540 after unification phase 1. No triple was found which is common for all the ontologies, 9 triples were common for several ontologies (exact matches), 8 of them belong to taxonomic (is-a and instance-of) relationship types, the ninth one is – (protestant, participates_in, demonstration). This complies with our expectation that it is easier to agree on taxonomic relations than on others. A list of exactly matching triples for two or more ontologies includes: (organization, is_a, object), (person, is_a, object), (Benjamin Netanyahu, instance_of, Prime Minister), (Dafni Lif, instance_of, head of the social protest), (religious sector, instance_of, sector), (demonstration, is_a, event of protest), (Israel, instance_of, country), (Tel-Aviv, instance_of, city), (protestant, participates_in, protest).

We further systematically compared 10 pairs of ontologies (for the 5 ontologies) according to different levels of similarity. The results are presented in Figure 2 and Table 1. Most of the unified pairs were added when applying the entailment rule. In Table 1, the first level of normalization is applied to the triples and not to individual terms as in Figure 2. After applying the second unification rule we calculated the number of triples with identical relationship types and hyponyms or hypernyms for terms. Then, we applied the next four unification rules to further increase the unification level of the ontologies and measured the amount of similar triples for each level. The results of every unification step are presented in Table 1. Overall, the highest inter-ontology matching level achieved is rather low (10% at the most, 6% on average). On the other hand, the inconsistency detection analysis yielded no contradictory statements between any pair of ontologies in our corpus, consequently leading to the conclusion that the rest of the triples are complementary.

Figure 2. Ontologies matching statistics at terms level for the “social protest” experiment for pairs of ontologies.

Table 1. Ontologies matching statistics for triples at different unification levels for 2011 experiment (the social protest).

Unification level / ontology pairs	After applying the 1st unification rule	After applying the 2nd unification rule	After applying the 3rd unification rule	After applying the 4th unification rule	After applying the 5th unification rule	After applying the 6th unification rule
1-2	2	11	12	12	19	22
1-3	1	5	6	9	16	19
2-3	3	10	12	12	18	19
2-4	1	2	3	3	5	6
2-5	5	6	9	9	14	17
3-4	2	4	4	7	10	11
5-4	1	2	3	3	5	5
1-4	0	4	7	7	8	10
1-5	1	2	4	5	11	14
3-5	2	3	3	6	8	8

In the “Jewish tradition” experiment with 9 subjects, 9 ontologies were constructed all using the same concept list (100 given concepts) and the same relationship type list (16 relationship types). However, every subject chose a different subset of the entities to be inserted into her personal ontology. As a result, the minimum number of common terms was 45. As shown in Figure 3 there was a high term similarity for most of the ontologies (76% agreement on average). 436 distinct triples exist in all the ontologies, but none of

them was common for all nine ontologies. The number of triples per ontology was: 86 for the 1st, 52 for the 2nd, 66 for the 3rd, 76 for the 4th, 59 for the 5th, 62 for the 6th, 80 for the 7th, 57 for the 8th and 104 for the 9th one.

Figure 3. Ontologies matching statistics at term level for the “Jewish tradition” experiment for pairs of ontologies.

The most popular (consensual) triples (appeared in 6-7 ontologies) were: (Fathers, figure, Torah); (Mothers, figure, Torah); (David Ben-Gurion, figure, Israeli state); (Tel-Aviv, location, Israel); (The old city, location, Jerusalem); (Jewish national fund, instance_of, Zionist organization). Three of them are related by figure, two by location and one by instance_of. Unification of synonyms (Rule 1.2) was not applied in this case, since the given terms correspond to classes and so do not contain synonyms. Eventually, the resulting ontologies (Table 2) were quite different (the average matching level for statements was 21% after applying all the unification rules), but no contradictions were detected either.

In respect to our additional research questions regarding the impact of pre-supplied information on the created ontologies and their inter-agreement and diverse viewpoint presentation, we obtained a few similar characteristics for the ontologies of the two experiments:

- (1) There was no common triple/statement for all the ontologies;
- (2) The most fruitful unification rule was the entailment unification - rule 5 (Tables 1, 2);
- (3) The most popular relationship types were instance_of and part_of (Tables 3, 4);
- (4) The most consensual relationship types out of the most popular ones were location and instance_of (both related to specific named entities);
- (5) The matching level for ontologies of subjects with similar views were not especially higher than for others;
- (6) The resulting ontologies were complementary having a large majority of disjoint triples.

Several differences between the two experiments were determined as well, thus indicating some influence of the various types of pre-supplied information. Interestingly, with an open vocabulary (Experiment 1) the subjects were able to build richer taxonomies - over 16% is_a and 23% instance_of relationships for Experiment 1 vs. less than 6% is_a and 13% instance_of triples for Experiment 2, but with lower consensus than for Experiment 2 (17.1% vs. 42.9% of triples common for at least two ontologies). In general, much

lower ontology similarity was achieved for Experiment 1 than for Experiment 2 (6% vs. 21% on average), as could be expected since some of the proposed rules tackle exactly the problem of semantic diversity and ambiguity. Surprisingly, despite the fact that the domains in both experiments were controversial no direct contradictions of types 1 and 2 were detected in the ontologies. Only one case of inconsistency of type 3 was observed: (Israel state foundation, cause-of, Independence war) vs. (Israel state foundation, result-of, Independence war).

Finally, we compared the obtained results to the relation-based ontology agreement measure by d'Aquin (2009) described in section 4 as a baseline. As can be observed from Tables 5 and 6 the proposed approach increased the agreement level between most of the ontologies. The differences between the matching levels of the baseline and the proposed ontology were found significant: (1) the greatest effect (over 300% on average [with \$p < 0.0001\$ for paired samples t-test](#)) on the agreement level was achieved for the social protest domain experiment with open vocabulary; (2) for the controlled vocabulary experiment our method yields about 10% increase in agreement on average ([with \$p < 0.01\$ for paired samples t-test](#)). Thus, in cases with high terminological diversity, which cannot be captured by the baseline approach, our rules become quite effective. However, it should be noted that the baseline considers all the partially terminologically matching triples (with different relationship types) as matching. Consequently, some of these triples do not represent semantically matching statements (e.g. (Zionist organization, goal, State of Israel) vs. (Zionist organization, agent, State of Israel) as contrary to our approach where all the considered triples are semantically similar or entailing. Hence, the actual improvement in semantic matching of ontologies yielded by our method is even higher.

Table 2. Ontologies matching statistics for triples at different unification levels for 2010 experiment (the "Jewish tradition" domain).

Unification level / ontologies	After applying the 1 st unification rule	After applying the 3rd unification rule	After applying the 4th unification rule	After applying the 5th unification rule	After applying the 6th unification rule
1 vs. 2	6	7	7	20	24
1 vs. 3	14	15	16	25	29
1 vs. 4	10	12	12	23	25
1 vs. 5	7	7	10	25	27
1 vs. 6	8	8	9	22	24
1 vs. 7	18	23	28	44	46
1 vs. 8	17	18	19	31	33
1 vs. 9	15	17	18	33	35
2 vs. 3	9	9	11	14	15
2 vs. 4	4	5	8	18	21
2 vs. 5	4	4	4	15	16
2 vs. 6	2	3	3	12	15
2 vs. 7	12	12	13	30	32
2 vs. 8	6	6	7	15	17
2 vs. 9	4	5	7	19	20
3 vs. 4	6	7	8	17	20
3 vs. 5	6	6	10	14	16

3 vs. 6	12	13	16	22	25
3 vs. 7	1	1	5	16	22
3 vs. 8	18	18	22	27	30
3 vs. 9	13	15	20	29	33
4 vs. 5	15	15	15	19	22
4 vs. 6	6	6	7	17	21
4 vs. 7	18	19	23	34	36
4 vs. 8	8	9	9	15	16
4 vs. 9	15	15	16	23	25
5 vs. 6	5	5	6	21	24
5 vs. 7	14	14	15	26	29
5 vs. 8	9	10	10	12	13
5 vs. 9	11	12	14	19	21
6 vs. 7	9	10	12	27	32
6 vs. 8	5	6	8	15	18
6 vs. 9	7	7	10	17	17
7 vs. 8	18	20	23	33	34
7 vs. 9	12	13	17	30	33
8 vs. 9	14	15	18	26	28

Table 3. The most consensual relationship types for the “social protest” experiment.

Relationship type	Total number of triples with the relationship type	Percentage of common triples
Location	27	37.0%
Instance of	159	31.5%
Demand of	8	25.0%
Represents	8	25.0%
Protests again	17	23.6%
Includes	10	20.0%
Isa	94	17.1%
Result of	12	16.7%
Participates in	15	13.4%
Part of	59	10.2%

Table 4. The most consensual relationship types for “Jewish tradition” experiment.

Relationship type	Total number of triples with the relationship type	Percentage of common triples
Child-parent	8	100%
Location	68	83.9%
Figure	59	67.8%
War	3	66.7%

Instance of	99	61.7%
Agent	21	47.7%
Associated with	82	47.6%
Part of	84	46.5%
Isa	35	42.9%
Goal	24	41.7%
Symbol	36	38.9%
Theme	67	35.9%
Instrument	11	27.3%
Make	11	18.2%
Manifestation	21	9.6%

Table 5: Baseline agreement level vs. unification rule-based agreement level for the social protest domain.

Ontologies	Unification rules-based agreement	Baseline agreement	Increase in agreement over the baseline in %
1-2	22	5	340
1-3	19	4	375
2-3	19	4	375
2-4	6	2	200
2-5	17	7	143
3-4	11	3	267
5-4	5	1	400
1-4	10	2	400
1-5	14	3	367
3-5	8	2	300

Table 6. Baseline agreement level vs. unification rule-based agreement level for the Jewish tradition domain.

Ontologies	Unification rules-based agreement	Baseline agreement	Increase in agreement over the baseline in %
1 vs. 2	24	24	0
1 vs. 3	29	27	7.5
1 vs. 4	25	25	0
1 vs. 5	27	24	12.5
1 vs. 6	24	23	4.4
1 vs. 7	46	41	12.2

1 vs. 8	33	32	3.2
1 vs. 9	35	34	3
2 vs. 3	15	13	15.4
2 vs. 4	21	18	16.7
2 vs. 5	16	16	0
2 vs. 6	15	15	0
2 vs. 7	32	31	3.3
2 vs. 8	17	16	6.3
2 vs. 9	20	18	11.2
3 vs. 4	20	18	11.2
3 vs. 5	16	18	-11.2
3 vs. 6	25	11	127.3
3 vs. 7	22	21	-14.3
3 vs. 8	30	35	4.8
3 vs. 9	33	28	17.9
4 vs. 5	22	22	0

4 vs. 6	21	20	5
4 vs. 7	36	32	12.5
4 vs. 8	16	16	0
4 vs. 9	25	25	0
5 vs. 6	24	23	4.4
5 vs. 7	29	28	3.6
5 vs. 8	13	13	0
5 vs. 9	21	20	5
6 vs. 7	32	30	6.7
6 vs. 8	18	16	12.5
6 vs. 9	17	14	21.5
7 vs. 8	34	31	9.7
7 vs. 9	33	29	13.8
8 vs. 9	28	25	12

4. Conclusion and future work

In this paper we explored the potential for maximizing the agreement between diverse ontologies for controversial domains. In these domains two contradictory statements might be both considered as truthful by different subjects who hold diverse viewpoints on the topic. To this end, we proposed a new paradigm for maximization of matching and unification of multiple ontologies based on their relations or statements. Consequently, if the ontologies express only similar and/or complementary sets of statements or facts, then they can be fully integrated into one model. Hence, the primary idea behind the introduced methodology is to identify and unify similar statements (defined explicitly or derived by the presented unification rules) into one representative statement, then to examine the rest of the statements for contradictions and merge all the complementary ones.

To empirically assess the validity of the introduced paradigm and in order to explore the impact of various information types on the ontology unification level, two initial experiments were arranged for construction of multiple personal ontologies on controversial domains by two groups of subjects. Then, the similarity between these ontologies was estimated according to the proposed multi-level unification scheme and compared to the baseline terminological similarity. Although in the conducted experiments the rules were applied in a semi-automatic manner, we showed the possible directions of their fully automatic implementation.

We found that the average similarity between ontologies increases when subjects are provided with pre-supplied classes and relationships, and also after applying various unification rules. However, similarity scores still remain quite low in absolute terms and the obtained ontologies are mostly complementary. With an open vocabulary both class and triple agreement is equally very low (6-7% on average), while with pre-supplied vocabulary the triples agreement has grown moderately to over 20%, but, as expected, the class similarity has increased dramatically to over 75% on average. Thus, even having virtually fully overlapping classes (the ideal situation), the product ontologies can be quite different with respect to the statements they represent. This finding supports our assumption that the existing approaches which concentrate mainly on class matching and unification do not lead to full unification at the semantic (statement-based) level even in the ideal case. For both domains, our agreement evaluation results show that the proposed approach significantly outperforms the baseline similarity and achieves much higher levels of inter-ontology agreement especially for the open vocabulary experiment.

On the other hand, when analysing popularity and relation matching for various relationship types, we found no dependency on the pre-supplied information. In other words, it is easier to reach a consensus for some relationship types than for the others independently of the experimental framework. We conclude that relationships (properties) are not influenced by either of the examined factors, classes are mostly affected by pre-supplied information, while relations are the most subjective (influenced by subject viewpoints) components of the ontology. Surprisingly, although the domains were highly controversial (comprising several contradictory viewpoints), as reflected by the low overall matching levels, only one case of explicit contradiction was detected in the diverse ontologies either, which means that different viewpoints co-exist in separate parts of the ontology and do not crossover. Hence, further ways of ontology diversification are to be proposed, such as statement generalization.

To conclude, this paper introduces the general framework for maximal semantic-level unification of ontologies by statements, supported by the positive results of the empirical feasibility test. The impact of this research is critical for many prominent ontology based applications (e.g. information retrieval, semantic search, annotation and summarization), especially for domains comprising diverse opinions, like news,

product reviews, medicine and cultural heritage content. The complete unified ontological model contains relations from multiple ontologies reflecting different aspects and viewpoints of the domain of knowledge. Consequently, when employed in multi-viewpoint search (Powell and French, 1998; Geryville, 2007) it will enhance discoverability and improve the quality of the obtained results. In particular, such ontology will help users learn which viewpoints exist on the specified query topic. As an illustration, given a query: "Prime minister and social protest", a list of a few relations from the ontology semantically related (but not necessarily terminologically similar) to the query concepts would be extracted and presented to the user as hyper-links (e.g. (Head of Government, attacks, social protest leaders); (Prime Minister, supports, social justice)) instead of the long list of unsorted articles. Each of these relations represents a certain viewpoint on the query topic. By selecting one of them, the corresponding articles which support this viewpoint will be displayed to the user.

In future work we intend to develop an automatic algorithm based on the presented unification rules for ontology unification by detection of matching, complementary and contradictory statements, e.g. by adaptation of lexical and textual entailment (Szpektor et al., 2008; Dagan et al., 2009; Stern and Dagan, 2012) and contradictory statement recognition techniques (Kawahara et al., 2010). Also, new evaluation criteria and framework for statement-based matching should be devised to assess its quality and compare it to the state-of-the-art entity-based matching methods. Further, the obtained unified ontology might be evaluated in terms of its contribution to the semantic search and other semantic web applications.

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Appendix

Table 7: Distinct concepts (classes and instances) from all the personal ontologies for experiment 1 (the social protest domain):

Robert Tiviaev	Lower housing costs	Eli Yishai	"If you want" organization
Ron Huldai	Lowering prices	Encampment	"My Israel" organization
Rothschild	Main tent protest	Event	A mass rally on July 30
Rothschild Boulevard	Margalit	Event protest	A mass rally on July 30

Rothschild encampment	Mass protest	Extension of maternity leave	Active encampment
Rothschild team	Mayor of Tel Aviv	Extreme left	Activist
Roy Neuman	Meir Shalev	Eyal Golan	Affordable Housing
Second and third readings	Member	Faction	Amos Oz
Sector	Member of Knesset	Falling prices	Anarchists
Semi-autonomous authority	Member of Parliament	Foreign Minister	apartment for rent
Semi-autonomous entity	Member of Protest	Foreign worker	Apartments
Settlement	Michael Eitan	Forum March 20 percentage 08.03.11	Apartments for Rent
Settlement	Middle class	Forward	Army
Settler	Million march	Free Education	Artist
Sheba Hospital	Minister	Free Health	Attack
Shlomo Artzi	Miri Regev	Free Market	Autonomy
Shlomo Molla	Moshe Gafni	Gasi Cohen	Avigdor Lieberman
Shows	Municipal authority	Gay Pride Parade in Jerusalem 28.7.11	Ayelet Maoz
Singer	Municipality	Geographic distribution	Barack Obama
Social Democracy	Naftali Bennett	Geographic location	Beer Sheva
Social housing law in central Israel	Nation	Geographical area	Ben Gurion University
Social Justice	National Student Union	Gilad Shalit	Ben-Gurion University
Social Protest	National Student Union Chairman	Government	Benjamin Netanyahu

Social Volcano	New Israel Fund	Government decisions	Bill
Social-political organization	Noam Shalit	Government of Israel	Bill on planning and construction
Society	Non-profit organization	Government Office	Bnei Akiva
Socio-economic change	Non-violent protest	Group	Budget
Soldier	North	Hadag Nahash	campaign
South	Object	Hadar Stern	Capital city
State Budget	Ofer Eini	Haifa	Capitalism
Stav Shafir	Ofri Raviv	Haredi sector	Carmel Shama
street	Opposition	Head of struggle	Center
Student	Organization	Head of tent protest	Center (geographical)
Student Association	Orthodox	Hierarchical Area	Center (hierarchical)
Students	Overthrow the government	Hierarchical division	Central Assembly
Sub - Organization	PA President	Holon	Central Region
Supertanker plan	Palestine	Home Office	CEO
Supervision of basic baby products	Parade wagons	Homeless	Chairman of Organization
Sushi eater	Parent	Homes for Sale	Chairman of the Finance Committee
Tel Aviv	Parents protest	Hospital	Chairman of the Israeli Labor Union
Tel Aviv University	Parliament	Housing	Chairman of the Israeli student union
Tent City	Password	Housing Minister	Chairman of the Student Association
Tent protest	Peace	Housing prices	Chairman of the Union of

			Students
Tents	Perception	Housing protest	Charity Fund
Terrorist	Periphery	Housing protest	Chief of staff
The capitalist	Person	Housing protest on Rothschild Boulevard	Citizen
The cottage cheese protest	Petah Tikva	Housing Reform	City
The fall in kindergarden prices	physician	Housing reforms	Coalition
The leaders of the housing protest	Place	Housing shortage	Combination factions
The religious	Police	Housing solution	Committee Chair
The roar of the people	Political circles	Idea	Communications
Trachtenberg	Population	Illegal demonstration	Congress
Trachtenberg Committee	Population group	Initiator	Contractor
Traditional public religious	Preliminary reading	Inspection	Convergence
Traffic disruptions	President	Institution	Cost housing
Treasury	President of the United States	Institution of higher education	Cost of living
Tycoon	Prime minister	Israel	Council of Jewish communities in Judea , Samaria and Gaza
Tzipi Livni	Privatization	Israel Land Administration	Country
Umann (city in Ukraine)	Protest	Israeli Knesset	Daphni Leef
Union of Students	Protest	Israeli resident	David Grossman

Union of Students at Ben Gurion	Protest deportation of foreign workers' children	Itamar Ben-Gvir	Decline in housing prices
United States	Protest group	Itzik Molly	Defense Budget
Uri Keidar	Protest Rally	Jerusalem	Defense Minister
Vice chairman of the National Students Union	Protest real estate	Jerusalem Municipality	Democracy
Vision of social justice	Protest tent	July 23 mass rally	Demonstration
Voting on the bill	Protest tent in Jerusalem	Kiryat - eight	Demonstration housing 7/23/11
Walk wagons	Protest wagons	Kiryat Arba	Demonstration of doctors at Ichilov July 23
Welfare	Public housing	Knesset	Demonstrations against the law of the Knesset August 3 models
Welfare state	Purchase apartment	Knesset committee	Demonstrator
Writer	Raananim organization	Knesset Interior and Environment	Disagreement
Yesha Council	Rabin Medical Center	Land	Distress
Yesha Council CEO	Ramat Gan	Law Models	doctor
Yishai Lapidot	Real Estate	Leads a protest group	Doctors protest
Yoav Galant	Reducing social gaps in Israel	Lease and Loan Act	Documentation Requirements
Yoram Kaniuk	Reducing the cost of living	Legislation	Dorms
Yotam Kellner	Reforms	Legislature	Dr. Leonid Eidelman
Young	Regev Contes	Levinsky tent	Dr. Oren Sagi

Young couples	Religious youth	Zionist	Liat Vardi Bar	Driver
Youth Movement	Renting apartment	an	Likud	Earmark
Yuval Steinitz	Resistance		Location	Economic Committee
Zion Place	Revolution		Lodging	Economic policy
	Rising prices		Lower class	Ehud Barak

Table 8: A list of the relationships from all the personal ontologies for the social protest domain:

Said by	Member	Event from	Abbreviation
Seal	No part of	Found in	Activity
Service	Not take place in	Geographic distribution of	Another word for
Serving in	Occupied by	Handles	Appointed by
Signed by	Operation	Head of	Attacks
Signed on	Opposed to	Head of struggle	Authority within
Some of	Participates in	Heads	Belongs to
Sponsors	Performed by	Human component	By means of
Status	Populates	Initiated	Charge of
Stems from	Purpose	Instance of	Collection of
Step in	Reach	IS-A	Component of
Structural division of	Related to	IS-Not	Congruent to
Supports	Replacement for	Leads	Consists of
Takes over	Represented by	Leads to	Containing
Takes place in	Represents	Learning in	Cutting of
The reason for	Requirement of	Live in	Director of
The result of	Responsible for	Located at	Disconnected from

Type of	Responsible for	Location in	Does not participate in
Votes for	Role in	Lowers	Does not support
Will report to	Role of	Managed by	Elected official in
Written by	Works in	Works to	

Table 9: A list of the concepts from all the personal ontologies for experiment 2 (Jewish tradition):

Twelve Tribes	Prayer	Islamic nation	Abraham
Ukraine	Prophet	Israel Holidays	Artist
War	Rabbi Nachman	Jacob	Bible
War of Independence	Rabbis	Jerusalem	Breslov
Wars of Israel	Rachel	Jewish Heritage	Building a Sukkah
Year of 1948	Rebecca	Jewish nation	Building land
Years of 2008-2009	Religion	Jewish	Capital city
Zionism	Religious Jews	Wedding	Cast Lead
Zionist Organization	Religious Zionism	Jews	Christianity
	Romans	Joshua	City
	Rome	Judaism	Commandment to help the poor
	Sarah	Land of Israel	Commandments
	Saturday	Leader	Conquest
	Seder	Lovers of Zion	Custom
	Settlement (building land)	Miracle	David Ben - Gurion
	State of Israel	Monotheistic religions	Declaration of Independence
	State of Israel	Mosque	Declaration of Independence
	Succoth	Mothers of the Nation	Destruction of the Temple
	Synagogue	Mount	Exodus
	Tel - Aviv	Muslims	Follower
	Temple	Nation	Four species
	Ten commandments	New Year	Fund
	Ten Tribes	Old town of Jerusalem	Fund
	The Ten Commandments	Pardons	Haggadah of Passover
	Thou shalt not bear false witness	Passover	Hebron
	Thou shalt not steal	Patriarchs	High Holidays
		Piety	

Three Habits	Pioneers	Holidays
Times of the Jewish calendar	Place of worship	Independence Day
Tired	Place of worship	Isaac
Torah	Practical Zionism	Islam

Table 10: A list of relationships from all the personal ontologies for the Jewish tradition domain:

agent	location
associated	make
child-parent	manfstation
figure	part-of
goal	symbol
Instance-of	theme
instrument	time
IS-A	cause